

Design and Implementation of 32 – bit RISC Processor using Xilinx

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Abstract: These RISC or Reduced Instruction Set Computer is a design philosophy that has become a mainstream in Scientific and engineering applications. The main objective of this paper is to design and implement of 32 – bit RISC (Reduced Instruction Set Computer) processor using XILINX VIRTEX4 Tool for embedded and portable applications. The design will help to improve the speed of processor, and to give the higher performance of the processor. The most important feature of the RISC processor is that this processor is very simple and support load/store architecture. The important components of this processor include the Arithmetic Logic Unit, Shifter, Rotator and Control unit. The module functionality and performance issues like area, power dissipation and propagation delay are analyzed using Virtex4 XC4VLX15 XILINX tool.

Keywords: Processor, Reduced Instruction Set Computer (RISC), VHDL, Xilinx 12.1, FPGA.

I. INTRODUCTION

A digital system was developed by using a set of interconnected digital integrated circuits like counters, buffers, logic gates and memory. It requires lots of analysis, testing and to adapt the design metrics like speed, response time, power consumption etc. which resulted very difficult for development. Also every design change implied a whole analysis and most times expensive.

Nowadays, computer and mobile phones is indispensable tool for most of everyday activities. This places an increasing burden on the embedded microprocessor to provide high performance while retaining low power consumption and small die size, which increase the complexity of the device [3]. However, as products grow in complexity more processing power is required while the expectation on battery life also increases.

With the rapid development of silicon technology RISC includes extensions to RISC concepts that help achieve given levels of performance at significantly lower cost than other systems. The main features of RISC processor are the instruction set can be hardwired [7] to speed instruction execution.

In the present work, the design of a 32-bit data width Reduced Instruction Set Computer (RISC) processor is presented. It has a complete instruction set, program and data memories, general purpose registers and a simple Arithmetical Logical Unit (ALU) for basic operations. In this design, most instructions are of uniform length and similar structure, arithmetic operations are restricted to CPU registers and only separate *load* and *store* instructions access memory. The architecture supports 16 instructions to support Arithmetic, Logical, Shifting and Rotational operations.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II explains System architecture of a 32 – bit RISC processor. Section III presents the implementation of modules of RISC processor and the simulation results implemented in advanced 90nm process technology. Section IV presents RISC Instruction set format. Section V discusses summary with the implementation of the RISC design topology. The final section presents the Conclusion and References.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE OF A 32 – BIT RISC PROCESSOR

The system architecture of a 32 - bit RISC processor is shown in Fig. 1. The RISC processor architecture consists of Arithmetic Logic Unit (ALU), Control Unit (CU), Barrel Shifter, Booth's Multiplier, Register File and Accumulator. RISC processor is designed with load/store (Von Neumann) architecture, meaning that all operations are performed on operands held in the processor registers and the main memory can only be accessed through the load and store instructions. One shared memory for instructions (program) and data with one data bus and one address bus between processor and memory [7]. Instruction and data are fetched in sequential order so that the latency incurred between the machine cycles can be reduced. For increasing the speed of operation RISC processor is designed with five stage pipelining. The pipelining stages are Instruction Fetch (IF), Instruction Decode (ID), Execution (EX), Data Memory (MEM), and Write Back (WB).

The function of the instruction fetch unit is to obtain an instruction from the instruction memory using the current value of the PC and increment the PC value for the next instruction. The main function of the instruction decode unit is to use the 32-bit instruction provided from the previous instruction fetch unit to index the register file and obtain the register data values. The instructions opcode field bits [31-26] are sent to a control unit to determine the type of instruction to execute. The type of instruction then determines which

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control signals are to be asserted and what function the ALU is to perform, thus decoding the instruction. The register file reads in the requested addresses and outputs the data values contained in these registers [1].

instruction opcode bits [31 – 26] and decodes the instruction to generate nine control signals to be used in the additional modules as shown in Fig. 3. The RegDst control signal determines which register is written to the register file. The Jump control signal selects the jump address to be sent to the PC. The Branch control signal is used to select the branch address to be sent to the PC. The MemRead control signal is asserted during a load instruction when the data memory is read to load a register with its memory contents. The MemtoReg control signal determines if the ALU result or the data memory output is written to the register file [1]. The ALUOp control signals determine the function the ALU performs. (e.g. and, or, add, sbu, slt) The MemWrite control signal is asserted when during a store instruction when a registers value is stored in the data memory [1]. The ALUSrc control signal determines if the ALU second operand comes from the register file or the sign extend. The RegWrite control signal is asserted when the register file needs to be written [1]. Table I shows the control signal values from the instruction decoded.

Fig. 1 System Architecture of a 32 - bit RISC processor

These data values can then be operated on by the ALU whose operation is determined by the control unit to either compute a memory address (e.g. load or store), compute an arithmetic result (e.g. add, and or slt), or perform a compare (e.g. branch). The control unit has two instruction decoders that decode the instruction bits and the decoded output of the control unit is fed as control signal either into Arithmetic logic unit (ALU) or Barrel shifter or Booth's Multiplier. If the instruction decoded is arithmetic, the ALU result must be written to a register. If the instruction decoded is a load or a store, the ALU result is then used to address the data memory. The final step writes the ALU result or memory value back to the register file.

III. MODULES DESIGN OF 32 - BIT RISC PROCESSOR

This section presents the design of different modules like Control Unit (CU), ALU, Universal Shift Register, barrel shifter, Booth's Multiplier and General Purpose Registers.

A. Control Unit

The control unit of the RISC processor examines the

Fig. 2 State Diagram of Control Unit

Fig. 3 RISC Control Unit

Table I RISC Control Signals

Instruction	RegDst	ALUSrc	MemtoReg	RegWrite	MemRead	MemWrite	Branch	ALUOp1	ALUOp0
R-type	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0
lw	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
sw	X	1	X	0	0	1	0	0	0
beq	X	0	X	0	0	0	1	0	1

The entire design of the Control Unit is represented in Fig. 4 and the timing waveform for arithmetic unit simulated using Xilinx tool is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 4 RTL Schematic of Control Unit (CU)

Fig. 5 Simulated Timing Diagram of Control Unit

B. Arithmetic Logic Unit (ALU)

The arithmetic/logic unit (ALU) executes all arithmetic and logical operations. The arithmetic/logic unit can perform arithmetic operations or mathematical calculations [7] like addition, and subtraction. As its name implies, the arithmetic/logic unit also performs logical operations include Boolean comparisons, such as AND, OR, XOR, NAND, NOR and NOT operations. Table II shows the select lines values from the instruction decoded and operation performed according to select lines.

Table II Operation of Arithmetic Logic Unit (ALU)

Select Lines Op (2:0)			Function Performed
Op(2)	Op(1)	Op(0)	Operation
0	0	0	ADD
0	0	1	SUB
0	1	0	NOT
0	1	1	NAND
1	0	0	NOR
1	0	1	AND
1	1	0	OR
1	1	1	XOR

The entire design of the ALU is represented in Fig.6 and the timing waveform for arithmetic unit simulated using Xilinx tool is shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 6 RTL Schematic of Airthmatic Logic Unit (ALU)

Fig. 7 Simulated Timing Diagram of Arithmetic Logic Unit

A. Barrel Shifter

The design consists of a total of eight 8x1 multiplexers. The output of one multiplexer is connected as input to the next multiplexer in such a way that the input data gets shifted in each multiplexer thus performing the rotation operation. Depending on the select lines the number of rotation varies. With select lines low there is no output. If select line c0 is high 1-bit rotation takes place, if c1 is high 3-bit rotation. The rotation of the input data for different select lines is shown in Table III. The Fig. 8 shows the top block of the barrel shift rotator. The timing waveform for Barrel Shifter simulated using Xilinx tool is shown in Fig. 9.

Table III Operation of Barrel Shifter

Select Lines			Output of Rotator							Function Performed	
S2	S1	S0	Q7	Q6	Q5	Q4	Q3	Q2	Q1	Q0	
0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1- Bit rotate
0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	3- Bit rotate
1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	5- Bit rotate
1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	7- Bit rotate

Fig. 8 RTL Schematic of Barrel Shifter

Fig. 9 Simulated Timing Diagram of Barrel Shifter

A. Booth's Multiplier

The Multiplier is implemented using the modified Booth algorithm. The two main advantages of this algorithm are speed and the ability to do signed multiplication (using two's complement) without any extra conversions. The entire design of the Booth Multiplier is represented in Fig. 10. The flowchart for Booth Algorithm is given in Fig. 11. Booth's algorithm uses an extra bit on the right of the least significant bit in the product register. This bit starts out as 0.

Fig. 10. RTL Schematic of Booth's Multiplier

Fig. 11 Flowchart of Booth Algorithm

The multiplier is implemented using the modified booth algorithm. The multiplier is scanned sequentially from right to left. In this case, however, three adjacent bits are examined during each step of the procedure. According to the value of the three bits, the multiplicand is added to or subtracted from the accumulated partial product and the later is then shifted. The timing waveform for Booth's Multiplier simulated using Xilinx tool is shown in Fig. 12.

Fig. 12 Simulated Timing Diagram of Booth's Multiplier

A. General Purpose Register

The eight bit input data is stored in this register. This register acts as a source register. The register file has two read and one write input ports, meaning that during one clock cycle [1], the processor must be able to read two independent data values and write a separate value into the register file. The register file was implemented in VHDL by declaring it as a one-dimensional array of 32 elements or registers each 8-bit wide. It consists of eight D – flip flops and eight AND gates. The gate level view of the register is given by Fig. 13. Taking CLOCK as low or high and RegWr as high the data is stored in the register. The simulated timing waveform in Fig. 14.

Fig. 13 RTL Schematic of Register File

Fig. 14 Simulated Timing Diagram of Register File

IV. RISC INSTRUCTION SET

RISC only has three instruction types: I-type is used for the Load and Stores instructions, R-type is used for Arithmetic instructions, and J-type is used for the Jump instructions [1] as shown in Fig. 15. Table IV provides a description of each of

the fields used in the three different instruction types. Arithmetic instructions or R-type include: ALU Immediate (e.g. addi), three-operand (e.g. add, and, slt), and shift instructions (e.g. sll, srl). The J-type instructions are used for jump instructions (e.g. j). Branch instructions (e.g. beq, bne) are I-type instructions which use the addition of an offset value along with the program counter (PC) to compute the branch target address; this is considered PC-relative addressing.

The most significant feature of instruction set is that all of instruction may be executed conditionally according to the condition flags. A condition field within all instructions is compared with the condition flag in program status register and the result of the comparison determines whether the instruction can be executed or not. This reduces the need for forward branches and allows very dense in-line code (without branches) to be written. In addition, shift operation is performed in serial with ALU in all data path cycles. This enables data processing instructions to execute various arithmetic operations using shift operation in one clock cycle [9].

Table IV RISC Instruction Fields

Field	Description
<i>opcode</i>	6-bit primary operation code
<i>rd</i>	5-bit specifier for the destination register
<i>rs</i>	5-bit specifier for the source register
<i>rt</i>	5-bit specifier for the target (source/destination) register or used to specify functions within the primary <i>opcode</i> REGIMM
<i>address/immediate</i>	16-bit signed <i>immediate</i> used for logical operands, arithmetic signed operands, load/store address byte offsets, and PC-relative branch signed instruction displacement
<i>instr_index</i>	26-bit index shifted left two bits to supply the low-order 28 bits of the jump target address
<i>sa</i>	5-bit shift amount
<i>function</i>	6-bit function field used to specify functions within the primary <i>opcode</i> SPECIAL

Fig. 15 RISC Instruction Types

V. SUMMARY

This section presents the performance of the processor in terms of its Total Power and Delay that are obtained using the Virtex4 XC4VLX15 XILINX tool. Table V presents the maximum power dissipation, area occupied and time taken by each module to operate the processor.

Table V Delay, Total Power and Area Calculation

Topology	Delay (ns)	Slices Utilized (Area)	AT	Power Dissipation $10^{-9}W$	Total Power (W)
Control Unit	0.905	15	13.575	0.159	0.165
ALU	4.495	60	269.7	0.159	0.168
Barrel Shifter	2.905	262	761.11	0.159	0.164
Booth's Multiplier	4.495	60	269.7	0.159	0.166
Register File	5.443	74	402.782	0.159	0.166
Total	18.243	471	8592.453		0.829

It is observed that the overall delay of the circuit is 18.243 ns. The maximum area is occupied by the Barrel Shifter and ALU. The overall power dissipation of this processor is observed to be 6.258 W. The power dissipation can even be reduced if the circuit is designed with any adiabatic logic. Fig. 16 and Fig. 17 show the variation of area, power dissipation and delay of the whole RISC processor and for each sub modules respectively. From the graph it is seen that the maximum power dissipation and chip area is exhibited by the ALU unit.

Fig. 16 Delay Estimation

Fig. 17 Area Estimation

VI. CONCLUSION

A 32-bit RISC processor [2] with 16 instruction set has been designed. Every instruction is executed in one clock cycles with 5-stage pipelining. The design is verified through exhaustive simulations. The processor achieves higher performance, lower area and lower power dissipation. This processor can be used as a systolic core to perform mathematical computations like solving polynomial and differential equations. Apart from this it can be used in portable gaming kits.

VII. REFERENCES

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